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1. Project Summary

The MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowship project LIGNIN-IB-PEROXIDASE (Proposal number: 101153909) addressed a major bottleneck in sustainable biomass valorisation: the inefficient utilization of lignin, a highly abundant yet underexploited renewable resource generated in large quantities by the pulp and paper industry. Despite the availability of fungal ligninolytic enzymes capable of degrading lignin under mild conditions, their industrial application remains limited due to low enzyme availability, insufficient stability under harsh process conditions, and high production costs. The overarching objective of this project was to establish a robust biotechnological platform to produce active ligninolytic peroxidases and to lay the groundwork for future enzyme engineering toward improved thermostability and alkaline pH tolerance.

The project initially proposed the use of artificial intelligence (AI)-assisted protein engineering to design improved variants of lignin peroxidase (LiP) and versatile peroxidase (VP), followed by heterologous expression in *Escherichia coli* as inclusion bodies (IBs), solubilization, refolding, and functional characterization. During the implementation phase, extensive experimental work was carried out to establish reliable upstream and downstream processes for wild-type peroxidases, which were required as essential benchmarks for subsequent engineering efforts.

Wild-type LiP, VP, manganese peroxidase (MnP) and dye-decolorizing peroxidase (DyP) were successfully cloned and expressed in *E. coli* as inclusion bodies. Comprehensive solubilization and refolding strategies were developed and optimized, with a particular focus on LiP and VP due to their high redox potential and relevance for non-phenolic lignin degradation. The refolding process was systematically improved through buffer optimization, controlled heme incorporation, and stabilization strategies, leading to the successful recovery of bioactive LiP at bioreactor scale. Refolded LiP exhibited high specific activity, correct heme incorporation, and biochemical characteristics comparable to established peroxidase benchmarks, demonstrating the technical feasibility of producing functional ligninolytic enzymes from bacterial inclusion bodies.

However, several scientific and methodological limitations became evident during the project. AI-driven protein engineering approaches were constrained by the limited number of known LiP and VP sequence variants, which restricted the availability of sufficiently large and diverse datasets required for reliable machine-learning-based optimization. In parallel, the use of bacterial inclusion bodies introduced an inherent ambiguity in the functional evaluation of engineered variants, as reduced activity could not be unambiguously attributed to sequence modifications or to misfolding during the refolding process.

To address these limitations and ensure methodological robustness, the project strategy was adapted to include the yeast *Pichia pastoris* as an alternative eukaryotic expression system. Secretory expression of LiP and VP in *P. pastoris* enabled proper folding and post-translational maturation of these heme-containing enzymes, thereby eliminating uncertainties associated with refolding from inclusion bodies. Functional wild-type LiP was successfully produced and purified from the yeast secretome, providing a reliable platform for future mutational studies where changes in activity can be confidently linked to sequence modifications rather than folding artifacts.

Overall, the project delivered significant advances in the production, refolding, and functional characterization of ligninolytic peroxidases, established scalable workflows for bioactive

enzyme recovery, and generated critical methodological insights that informed strategic adjustments to the original work plan. These outcomes provide a solid experimental foundation for future protein engineering efforts aimed at developing robust enzymatic solutions for sustainable lignin valorization.

2. Work Performed and Achievements

2.1 Objectives and Work Plan

Research problem: Globally, 50-70 million tons of lignin, a highly branched heteroaromatic polymer, are discharged per year as a waste material from the paper and pulp industry despite being touted as the most abundant renewable source of different value-added products on earth. Leaving 98% of lignin underutilized, industries degrade only 2% of lignin and that also comes with environmentally hazardous thermochemical processes.

Background: Recently, the discovery of heme-containing class II fungal peroxidases viz. lignin peroxidase (LiP), manganese peroxidase (MnP), versatile peroxidase (VP), dye-decolorizing peroxidase (DyP) garnered a lot of attention due to their biodegradable ligninolysis. However, the industrial application of peroxidase-based lignin degradation still seems to be a far-flung dream owing to low availability of peroxidases in sufficient amount, enzyme instability in industrial effluent, high enzyme cost and long process times.

Aims and objectives: We hypothesized that a cocktail of engineered stress tolerant, active and stable peroxidases could lead to synergistic biodegradation of lignin. To achieve this, artificial intelligence (AI) tailored LiP, MnP, VP and DyP were planned to be cloned and expressed as inclusion bodies (IBs) in *E. coli* using Prof. Spadiut's expertise whereas I aimed to employ solubilization and refolding strategies to increase the overall yield of bioactive protein (Fig. 1). An ideal stoichiometric combination of engineered peroxidases was planned to be standardized to withstand the harsh conditions of industrial effluent, resulting in a sustainable and economic ligninolytic technology.

Fig. 1: Recovery steps for the stress-tolerant, stable and active engineered peroxidases from bacterial IBs.

2.2 Work Performed

To achieve the objectives, the wild type LiP (wtLiP), MnP (wtMnP), VP (wtVP) and DyP (wtDyP) were required which could serve as internal controls against respective engineered ligninolytic enzymes in terms of bioactivity and stability at different pH and temperature. Since these wild type ligninolytic enzymes were not commercially available neither as heterologously expressed nor in their native form, it was decided to produce these enzymes first at small scale followed by large scale in bacterial and yeast system. Moreover, a bioactive ligninolytic enzyme optimized at pilot scale could serve as an opportunity for commercialization.

2.2.1 Small scale production of wild type ligninolytic enzymes expressed as bacterial inclusion bodies

The aforesaid ligninolytic enzymes were originally discovered and characterized in the different fungi as mentioned in Table 1. Since all these ligninolytic enzymes in nature are extracellularly secreted to degrade the lignin, each of them had a signal sequence in their native form. Since the aim of the project was to express the ligninolytic enzymes as bacterial inclusion bodies, the signal sequence associated with each of the enzymes were eliminated in their nucleotide sequence and sent for cloning to GenScript Biotech (order number: U913P615G0). These *E. coli* clones containing four wild type ligninolytic enzymes were further investigated at small scale for overexpression as bacterial IBs and their solubilization and refolding profile. wtLiP and wtVP were further investigated for its stability and activity. The recovery of bioactive horse radish peroxidase (HRP) from bacterial IBs was already optimized in the host laboratory and hence it was used as an internal positive control for all the experiments (Humer et al., 2020).

Table 1: Intrinsic properties of wild type LiP, MnP, VP and DyP without its signal sequence and their mode of action (Wang et al., 2018)

Properties\Proteins	LiP	MnP	VP	DyP
EC no.	1.11.1.14	1.11.1.13	1.11.1.16	1.11.1.19
Protein name	LIPB	MNP1	VPL1	DyP1
UniProt ID	P31838	Q02567	Q9UR19	I2DBY1
Enzyme discovered and characterized in	<i>Phanerodontia chrysosporium</i> (Nie et al., 1998)	<i>Phanerodontia chrysosporium</i> (Whitwam & Tien, 1996)	<i>Pleurotus eryngii</i> (Camarero et al., 1999)	<i>Bjerkandera adusta</i> (Liers et al., 2010)
Molecular weight (kDa)	37,26	37,58	34,68	50,35
Aliphatic index	75,87	77,49	82,08	74,54
GRAVY	-0,165	-0,013	0,047	-0,225
Instability index	46,22	43,44	52,49	27,57
Disulfide bonds	4	5	4	0
Theoretical pI	4,71	4,66	4,44	4,54
Number of glycosylation site(s)	1	3	1	4

Cofactor(s)	Heme b and Ca ²⁺	Heme b, Mn ²⁺ and Ca ²⁺	Heme b, Mn ²⁺ and Ca ²⁺	Heme b
No. of cofactor binding sites	10	13	14	1
Nature of active site	Proton acceptor	Proton acceptor	Proton acceptor	Proton acceptor
Phenolic lignin	+++	+++	+++	++
Non-Phenolic lignin	+++	+	+++	++
Redox potential (V)	~1.28 – 1.40	~1.00 – 1.20	~1.33	~1.23 – 1.27
Mediator	Veratryl alcohol (VA)	Mn ³⁺	-	-
Remarks	Best for non-phenolic lignin, can degrade phenolic lignin also	Best for phenolic lignin	Most versatile without mediator	Excellent for dye decolorization

2.2.1.1 Overexpression of wtLiP, wtMnP, wtVP and wtDyP in *E. coli* as bacterial inclusion bodies: Four different *E. coli* constructs were induced with IPTG for corresponding overexpression of the gene of interest and their cell mass was subject to sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) based shearing of the cells as demonstrated in Fig. 2a. The green arrow in all the SDS-PAGE figures demonstrate the expected protein of interest. The proteome was loaded onto SDS-PAGE for observing the protein of interest. As observed in the Fig. 2b, the uninduced and induced load is not comparable to each other and there is no visible overexpression of the gene of interest. It may be due to different amount of proteome per dry cell weight of uninduced and induced cells for a given construct which could not be balanced out even though the induced cell pellet was diluted two times as compared to uninduced cell pellet (Fig. 2a). Hence, it cannot be concluded whether there was any expression of protein of interest.

Fig. 2: SDS-PAGE analysis of over-expression of each ligninolytic enzyme: a) A schematic representation of SDS based cell lysis. b) SDS-PAGE analysis of proteome of each microbial cell factory uniquely expressing each ligninolytic enzyme. The final supernatant from SDS based cell lysis was loaded onto SDS-PAGE for uninduced and induced cells. c) SDS-PAGE analysis of each peroxidase after breaking open the cells using homogenizer while HRP serving as an internal positive control. d) Solubilization profile of each of the peroxidase expressed as bacterial IBs.

Since bacterial IBs are relatively dense in nature as compared to host cell proteome, it is anticipated to have the insoluble protein as pellet after high-speed centrifugation if there was any expression as IBs. To validate this, the microbial cell factories were broken open using homogenizer and centrifuged at 20000xg. As observed in the Fig. 2c, the cell free extract (CFE) or the soluble part of proteome did not show any protein of interest. However, the insoluble part, also known as bacterial IBs, are visible at its respective place in SDS-PAGE. This was further confirmed after solubilizing the bacterial IBs in strong denaturant like 8 M urea and loading the solubilized IBs of each protein onto SDS-PAGE (Fig. 2d). Overall, this confirmed the expression of desired ligninolytic proteins as bacterial IBs.

After the confirmation of ligninolytic enzymes expressing as bacterial IBs, it was decided to focus on the enzymes that are more potent to degrade lignin over others. Lignin is composed of phenolic (~10%) and non-phenolic (~90%) structural units wherein the non-phenolic

counterpart is the most recalcitrant to degradation (Brunow & Lundquist, 2010). An enzyme with high redox potential can essentially oxidize the non-phenolic subunits and hence majority of lignin (Martínez et al., 2009). Therefore, further experiments were carried out with LiP and VP as enzymes of interest, not only due to their inherently high redox potential but also due to their smaller number of glycosylation sites which is helpful while expressing protein in *E. coli* (Table 1).

2.2.1.2 Solubilization and refolding of wtLiP and wtVP: As observed in Fig. 2c, the bacterial IBs of LiP and VP had a lot of host cell proteins as contaminant. Therefore, the IBs were subject to washing in the presence of 2 M urea and 500 mM NaCl to strip off loosely bound host proteins, chaperones, membrane fragments, lipids and detach DNA, RNA, and charged host cell proteins sticking to the IB surface. The removal of host proteins can be observed in lane 2, 3 and 4 of Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: SDS-PAGE analysis of processing a) HRP, b) LiP and c) VP from breaking open the bacterial cells to refolding the protein

To maximize the solubilization, the IBs of LiP and VP were solubilized at extremely alkaline pH (Singh et al., 2008). Furthermore, both bacterial IBs were solubilized in the presence of reducing agent like dithiothreitol (DTT) owing to presence of disulfide bonds (Table 1). Finally, the solubilized IBs were subject to refolding. Preliminary recipe of refolding buffer contained oxidized glutathione to rebuild the correct disulfide bonds, CaCl_2 and hemin as a cofactor. The pH of glycine buffer was set to be 9.5 to minimise the pH shock while refolding and stay away from isoelectric point (pI) of LiP and VP (Table 1). Despite all this, the refolded protein of both LiP and VP had some visible protein aggregates in the solution which were centrifuged down and clear supernatant was processed further.

2.2.1.3 Biochemical characterization of wtLiP and wtVP: The presence of insoluble aggregates posed the risk of soluble aggregates as well in the refolded protein. To determine this, SEC-HPLC was performed. Since the molecular weight of HRP (~35 kDa) is almost same as that of LiP and VP (~37 kDa), there is a major peak around 12 minutes which signifies the presence of folded LiP and VP (Fig. 4a). However, there are some minor peaks around 5-8 minutes also which represent the void volume of SEC-HPLC column and elution in that range signifies the presence of soluble aggregates in LiP and VP. The purity of the folded LiP and VP calculated from the area under curve turned out to be 20.5% and 33.5%.

Since there was some degree of refolded protein, it was of interest to determine if LiP and VP are bioactive. Hence, the LiP, VP and HRP were concentrated and ABTS based activity assay was set up. Peroxidases use hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) to oxidize a substrate. In this assay, the

substrate is ABTS (2,2'-azinobis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid)). When ABTS gets oxidized, it turns into a green/blue radical cation (ABTS•⁺) that absorbs strongly in the visible range. The faster the color appears, the higher the peroxidase activity. As observed in the Fig. 4b, all the peroxidases provided increment in the OD at 420 nm with respect to time. However, the measurements were not reliable because the wells of LiP and VP got turbid owing to instability of the both the peroxidases in the activity assay.

Fig. 4: Biochemical analysis of refolded LiP, VP and HRP: a) HPLC analysis of LiP (blue line) and VP (magenta line) whereas HRP (reddish brown line) and Milli Q (black line) served as a positive and negative control respectively. b) ABTS based activity assay of LiP (blue line) and VP (orange line) along with positive control HRP (grey line).

Table 2: Reinheitszahl (Rz) value for different peroxidases

	Dilution Factor	A ₂₈₀	A ₄₀₄	Rz
Ref LiP	1	0.793	0.375	0.47
Ref VP	1	0.815	0.348	0.43
Ref HRP	1	0.483	0.675	1.4
Conc LiP	10	0.571	0.3	0.52
Conc VP	20	0.557	0.276	0.5
Conc HRP	10	0.662	0.902	1.36

In order to determine the hemin integration in the folded LiP and VP, Reinheitszahl (Rz) value ($A_{404/280}$) for peroxidases was determined. As reported in Table 2, the Rz value for HRP is ~1.4 for both refolded and concentrated protein that represents

better hemin incorporation in the folded structure of HRP than that of LiP and VP. In the case of LiP and VP, the hemin was an integral part of the refolding mixture in contrast to HRP refolding procedure wherein hemin is added after partial refolding. It was hypothesized that hemin added in the refolding mixture of LiP and VP might have interfered with early refolding and caused aggregation. Thus, it was decided to add hemin after partial refolding of LiP and VP.

Since the refolded LiP and VP were not stable in refolding buffer (RB1: 10 mM CaCl₂ + 1 mM GSSG + 20 mM glycine at pH 10) as observed the insoluble aggregates visibly and soluble aggregates SEC-HPLC (Fig. 4), low concentration of stabilizers like urea and glycerol in the refolding mixture (RB2: 10 mM CaCl₂ + 1 mM GSSG + 2 M urea + 7% glycerol + 20 mM glycine at pH 10) was added and the aggregation tendency was studied. The solubilized LiP and VP were refolded in different buffers viz. RB1 and RB2 as depicted in the schematic diagram (Fig. 5a). The UV-vis spectrophotometric analysis revealed that the refolded protein recovered after refolding in RB2 buffer was almost 4 times more than that of recovered in RB1 which underlines the importance of low concentration of stabilizers in the refolding mixture of RB2.

Fig. 5: Optimization of refolding buffer: a) Schematic representation of refolding process. b) UV-Vis spectrophotometric analysis of aggregation tendency of LiP and VP in two different refolding buffers.

Since LiP and VP are natively active in acidic pH and theoretical isoelectric point (pI) of both the enzymes is ~4.7 (Table 1), the pH of RB2 buffer was reduced from 10 to 3. In such a case, there were almost no visible aggregates in the medium and further experiments were carried out with optimized refolding buffer RB2 (10 mM CaCl₂ + 1 mM GSSG + 7% glycerol + 150 mM NaCl + 2 M urea @ pH 3).

2.2.2 Large scale production of wtLiP as bacterial inclusion bodies

Having optimized the unit operations as mentioned in Table 3, the scale up experiments were carried out in the bioreactor.

Table 3: Unit operations for the final production process of LiP and VP from *E. coli* inclusion bodies

Material	Method
Inducer concentration: 1 mM IPTG DeLisa Medium	Incubation at 37°C, 230 RPM for 24 h
Lysis buffer: 50 mM Tris/HCl; 500 mM NaCl; 1.5 mM EDTA at pH 8	Homogenizer at >1200 bar for 2 minutes followed by centrifugation at 20000xg

Washing buffer: 500 mM NaCl; 1,5 mM EDTA; 50 mM Tris/HCl	Washing for 10 minutes followed by centrifugation at 20000xg
Solubilization buffer: 6 M urea + 20 mM glycine @ pH 3	Incubation for 1 h followed by centrifugation at 20000xg
Refolding buffer: 10 mM CaCl ₂ + 1 mM GSSG + 7% glycerol + 150 mM NaCl + 2 M urea @ pH 3	Incubation for 24 h @ 4°C followed by addition of 10 μM hemin chloride

2.2.2.1 Fed-batch based production of wtLiP in bioreactor: From the 30 h of batch time, the weight of wet bacterial pellet was 98,92 gm. An aliquot of bacterial pellet was taken as mentioned in Table 4 and IBs were washed thoroughly as demonstrated in Fig. 6b. With each washing, it can be observed that there was a loss of host proteins (Fig. 6b) that also corroborated with decreasing wet weight with respect to each succeeding step (Table 4). The washed IBs were solubilized and refolded as explained in Table 3. The protein concentration and amount for each processing step were estimated using Bradford assay as listed in Table 5. The refolded protein was set up for biophysical and biochemical characterization.

It is important to note that ImageJ-based densitometric analysis of SDS-PAGE gels was initially planned for protein quantification. However, co-expression of host proteins resulted in complex banding patterns that hindered reliable protein-specific quantification. The methodology was therefore adapted to Bradford-based total protein determination to ensure reproducible and robust normalization across samples.

Fig. 6: Large scale production of LiP as bacterial inclusion bodies: a) EVE software interface showing real-time monitoring and control parameters of the bioreactor during cultivation. b) SDS-PAGE analysis from breaking open the bacterial cells to solubilization.

Sample	Wet pellet (g)
Bacterial pellet	6,04
IB pellet	1,26
IB after wash 1	1,19
IB after wash 2	1,02
IB after H ₂ O wash	1,02

Table 4: Wet weight of each processing step for getting the clean IBs

Table 5: Protein estimation of different IB processing steps involved in the recovery of bioactive protein from bacterial IBs of wtLiP

Sample	Conc (mg/mL)	Volume (mL)	Amount (mg)
Total protein	9,84	40	393,6
Cell Free Extract	8,26	40	330,4
Wash 1	0,6	10	6
Wash 2	0,22	10	2,2
Water wash	0,14	5	7
Solubilized protein (6 M urea)	1,3	20	26
Refolded protein	0,125	2	0,25

2.2.2.2 Biophysical and biochemical characterization of wtLiP produced from fed-batch bioreactor: It was of interest to determine the impact of refolding over the period and correct time to add hemin in the partially refolded wtLiP. Therefore, real time intrinsic tryptophan fluorescence was recorded for entire refolding duration using fluorescence spectroscopy. From the Fig. 7a, it was evident that there is a blue shift in the fluorescence spectra with increasing time which is attributed to the fact that the native tryptophan residues are getting buried in the core of the protein. This signifies the protein getting refolded. It was also interesting to observe that most of the refolding took place in initial 5 h of incubating the solubilized LiP in RB2 at pH 3, further reducing the processing time of recovering active LiP. After incubating with

Fig. 7: Biophysical and biochemical characterization of refolded LiP: Intrinsic tryptophan fluorescence emission spectra (intensity vs. wavelength) of the LiP protein (upper box) and time-dependent shift in fluorescence emission wavelength during the refolding process (lower box) before (a) and after (b) hemin addition. c) ABTS-based enzyme activity assay showing the change in absorbance at 420 nm

(OD₄₂₀) as a function of time. d) List of proteins identified by LC–MS/MS analysis, including the target protein LiP, along with corresponding peptide matches and confidence parameters.

hemin, there was a further blue shift in the fluorescence spectra with increasing time which reinforces additional compactness and thus refolding of the LiP (Fig. 7b). This might have happened because the integration of hemin in the partially folded LiP would have made partially folded LiP into completely folded LiP. Most of the hemin integration also happened approximately within 5 h of hemin incubation (Fig. 7b).

After a successful protein refolding, it was of interest to determine whether the protein folded correctly and bioactive. Therefore, ABTS based activity assay was setup against pHRP as a positive control and refolding buffer RB2 as negative control. As observed in Fig. 7c and Table 6, the refolded LiP turned out to be active and stable. Further LC-MS characterization as depicted in Fig. 7d revealed the presence of LiP, confirming LiP as a bioactive enzyme in refolded buffer.

Table 6: Refolded LiP attributes

Concentration (mg/ml)	0,125
Total activity (U/ml)	153,25
Specific activity (U/mg)	1226,05
Reinheitszahl (Rz)	1,41

2.2.3 Large scale production of wtVP as bacterial inclusion bodies

Even if the refolded LiP turned out to be biologically active, quantitatively speaking, the amount of refolded LiP was hardly 0,25 mg per 6 gm of bacterial pellet (Table 4 and 5). Moreover, the refolded LiP was also not a major protein in the refolded protein species (section 2.2.1.3). It was decided to investigate other bacterial media to circumvent this situation. So terrific broth and a minimal media with slight modifications (Table S2) were tried out while keeping the downstream process identical as mentioned in Table 3. From the Fig. 8a and Fig. 8b, it was clear that there is a better production of IBs with both the medium as compared to Fig. 3c. However, the lane 7 of minimal media (Fig. 8b) showed better recovery after solubilizing the IBs of wtVP than terrific broth media (Fig. 8a). Moreover, the minimal media was more tuneable for scaled up experiments and hence the minimal media was finalized for further experiments.

Fig. 8: SDS-PAGE analysis of expressed VP in two different media composition viz. a) terrific broth and b) minimal media

The wtVP was produced in 10 L bioreactor wherein the 282.2 g of wet bacterial cells were harvested after 24 h of induction (Fig. 9a). Since the incubation time also affects the quality and quantity of IBs formed in the microbial cell factories, it was of interest to determine the ideal time of induction before the cells are harvested. Quantitatively speaking, from Fig. 9b and Table 7, it was clear that ideal time to harvest the cells could be between 4 – 6 h of post induction.

Table 7: The impact of VP IB production with respect to time

Parameters	2 h induced sample	4 h induced sample	6 h induced sample	24 h induced sample
OD	33,2	35	33,5	30,4
Wet IBs per gm of the bacterial pellet	0,1875	0,1886	0,235	0,3
Protein present (mg)	1,63	2,09	2,01	1,63

Fig. 9: Large scale production of VP as bacterial inclusion bodies: a) LUCULLUS software interface displaying real-time bioreactor parameters such as pH, dissolved oxygen, weight of base etc. b) SDS-PAGE analysis of VP IBs retrieved after 2 h, 4 h, 6 h and 24 h of induction with 1 mM IPTG.

The project originally aimed to engineer lignin peroxidase (LiP) and versatile peroxidase (VP) variants with improved thermostability and alkaline pH tolerance, using AI-driven protein engineering approaches in combination with heterologous expression and refolding from bacterial IBs. During the project, LiP and VP were successfully expressed in *E. coli* as inclusion bodies and extensive efforts were undertaken to obtain active enzymes through refolding and

biochemical characterization. However, several scientific and methodological limitations became apparent as the work progressed.

First, the application of AI-based protein engineering approaches proved constrained by the limited availability of LiP and VP sequence variants across organisms. Effective machine-learning-based optimization requires sufficiently large and diverse datasets for model training, which are currently not available for ligninolytic peroxidases. The small number of known isoforms significantly reduced the feasibility and predictive reliability of AI-driven design approaches and outsourcing such workflows required extensive domain-specific expertise and iterative experimental feedback that could not be efficiently implemented within the project timeframe.

In addition, the use of bacterial IBs introduced a fundamental ambiguity in the interpretation of activity data for engineered variants. Even if engineered LiP or VP constructs were successfully expressed and refolded from inclusion bodies, it was not possible to unambiguously distinguish whether reduced or absent enzymatic activity arose from improper refolding and misfolding during the refolding process, or from correctly folded but intrinsically less active engineered proteins. This limitation posed a significant challenge for reliable evaluation of mutational effects and risked confounding structure–function relationships.

To address this methodological limitation, the project strategy was adapted to employ *Pichia pastoris* as a eukaryotic expression system for secreted LiP and VP. Secretion-based expression in *P. pastoris* provides a more reliable folding and maturation environment for heme-containing peroxidases, thereby eliminating uncertainties associated with refolding from bacterial IBs. This approach allows observed changes in enzymatic activity to be attributed with higher confidence to sequence modifications rather than to folding artifacts.

Consequently, subsequent experimental work focused on optimization of the *P. pastoris* expression system to obtain functional wild-type LiP and VP as a prerequisite for future mutational studies. This strategic adjustment ensured methodological robustness and reproducibility of activity measurements and reflects a scientifically justified reassessment of experimental feasibility rather than a deviation from the overarching research goals.

2.2.4 Small scale production of wtLiP and wtVP as secretome of *Pichia pastoris*

Construction of expression cassettes and vectors for peroxidase expression in *Komagataella phaffii*, also known as *Pichia pastoris*, was carried out by following the GoldenPiCS method [10]. Synthesis of codon optimized coding sequences for LiP and VP has been ordered at Genscript (order no.: U668J852G0). These coding sequences have been further combined with one constitutive GAP promoter and one methanol inducible AOX promoter, yielding four constructs for expression in *K. phaffii*: GAP_LiP, GAP_VP, AOX_LiP and AOX_VP.

The colonies of LiP and VP with GAP promoters were grown in the different concentration of zeocin antibiotics. Each of these colonies were grown in 1 mL of YPD media for 72 h and it was anticipated to have the protein of interest viz. LiP and VP as a part of secretome in the culture medium. The secretome was analysed on SDS-PAGE as shown in Fig. 10a. The protein of interest appeared to be slightly above the green arrow. This may be due to post translational modifications introduced during production in *Pichia pastoris* as contrary to *E. coli*. LiP was produced almost same at almost all the concentration of zeocin. However, the VP was produced at 500 ug/ml concentration of zeocin. The higher concentration of zeocin might have led to

higher copy number of desired VP into host genome and hence that led to greater expression of VP. However, this effect was not very pronounced in the case of LiP.

Unlike bacterial IBs, these expressed proteins in *Pichia* system should be already folded and glycosylated, a preliminary ABTS based activity assay was set up for the different secretome to assess the activity. Initial results from Fig. 10b revealed that the highest level of activity was observed in the clone of LiP with 100 ug/ml of zeocin concentration whereas any clone of VP did not give any activity.

Fig. 10: Quantitative and qualitative analysis of LiP and VP expressed in *P. pastoris*: a) SDS-PAGE analysis of LiP and VP grown at different concentration of zeocin (50-500 ug/ml) for 72 h along with empty vector control. b) ABTS-based activity assay showing OD₄₂₀ versus time for different enzyme samples.

Based on these results, it was scaled up to 100 mL of culture media and assess the activity. Both LiP and VP were grown in the 100 mL of culture media at a concentration of zeocin to be 100 ug/ml. The secretome from both LiP and VP culture media underwent the gravity-based Ni-NTA chromatography. From Fig. 11a, the eluted fraction of LiP viz. 250 mM and 100 mM imidazole gave the significant activity as compared to negative controls. However, there was very less to negligible activity in the purified fractions of VP (Fig. 11b).

Fig. 11: ABTS based activity assay of purified (a) LiP and (b) VP expressed as secretome in *P. Pastoris*

Conclusions

The MSCA project LIGNIN-IB-PEROXIDASE aimed to establish a sustainable and scalable platform for the production and engineering of ligninolytic peroxidases to enable environmentally friendly lignin valorization. Although the fellowship concluded earlier than originally planned, substantial scientific and methodological progress was achieved.

During the project period, key upstream and downstream processes for the heterologous production of lignin peroxidase (LiP) and versatile peroxidase (VP) were successfully developed and optimized. Expression in *Escherichia coli* as inclusion bodies, followed by systematic solubilization and refolding strategies, enabled recovery of bioactive enzyme and validated the technical feasibility of recombinant production workflows. These results provide an important foundation for scalable enzyme manufacturing.

In parallel, critical methodological insights were gained regarding the practical limitations of AI-driven protein engineering for ligninolytic peroxidases, particularly due to restricted sequence diversity and data availability. Furthermore, the inherent ambiguity associated with refolding proteins from bacterial inclusion bodies prompted a strategic transition to the eukaryotic expression system *Pichia pastoris*, enabling secretion-based production and more reliable functional assessment. This adaptation strengthened the experimental platform and reduced risks associated with misfolding-related artefacts.

While the originally proposed AI-guided engineering and multi-enzyme cocktail optimization could not be fully realized within the shortened timeframe, the project successfully established the essential experimental and conceptual groundwork required for future engineering efforts. The generated workflows, optimized expression strategies and methodological refinements represent durable outcomes that extend beyond the project's duration.

Beyond the scientific achievements, the fellowship significantly enhanced expertise in bioprocess development, recombinant protein production and technology translation. The knowledge exchange between the researcher and the host institution contributed to strengthening technical competencies and expanding collaborative capacity.

Overall, despite early termination, the project delivered meaningful scientific advances and established a robust platform for continued development of stress-tolerant ligninolytic enzymes. The outcomes contribute to the long-term objective of enabling sustainable and economically viable biotechnological solutions for lignin valorization.

Supplementary information

Table S1: DeLisa medium composition

DeLisa Medium	final conc. [g/l]	stock conc [g/l]	stock add. [ml/l]	weigh in/add
C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₆ * H ₂ O	8,80	-	-	8,80
KH ₂ PO ₄	13,30	-	-	13,30
(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	4,00	-	-	4,00
Citric acid	1,70	-	-	1,70

MgSO ₄ * 7 H ₂ O (stock 500 x)	1,20	600,00	2,00	2,00
Fe(III) citrate (stock 100 x)	0,1000	10,00	10,00	10,00
EDTA (stock 100 x)	0,0084	0,84	10,00	10,00
Zn(CH ₃ COO) ₂ * 2 H ₂ O (stock 200 x)	0,0130	2,60	5,00	5,00
TE (stock 200 x)	-	-	5,00	5,00
Thiamine HCl (stock 1,000 x)	0,0045	4,50	1,00	1,00
Ampicillin (Stock 1000x)	0,0100	10,00	1,00	1,00

Table S2: Minimal medium composition with slight modifications [11]

S. No.	Media inoculum	composition	Concentration in g/L	Coefficient for 1g Dry Cell Weight (DCW)	Concentration designed per liter of medium for DCW 3g/L	Medium Inoculum total requirement (1,2 Liter Medium)
1	Potassium phosphate [g]	dihydrogen	3,00	XXXX	3,00	3,60
2	Dipotassium phosphate * 3H ₂ O [g]	hydrogen	6,00	XXXX	6,00	7,20
3	Yeast extract [g]		XXXX	0,15	0,45	0,54
4	Na-Citrate * 2H ₂ O [g]		XXXX	0,25	0,75	0,90
5	Mg-Sulfate * 7H ₂ O [g]		XXXX	0,10	0,30	0,36
6	Ca-Chloride * 2H ₂ O [g]		XXXX	0,02	0,06	0,07
7	Trace element solution [μl]		XXXX	50	150	180,00
8	Ammonium sulfate [g]		XXXX	0,45	1,35	1,62
9	Ammonium chloride [g]		XXXX	0,37	1,11	1,33
10	Glucose-Monohydrate [g]		XXXX	3,33	9,99	11,99

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